

1 The turbulent behaviour of Mr. Trump

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14 The word “turbulence” or “turbulent” was used for a long time for the unpredictable
15 behavior of children or of a crowd. Today, it is widely used to describe not only the
16 status of physical systems, such as turbulent flows, but also financial fluctuations, or
17 societal systems that lie between order and disorder. For the latter cases, the col-
18 lected data are often too short to do a good analysis. Here, using the number of false
19 or misleading claims by Mr. Trump, the ex-president of the United States of America
20 by the *Washington Post*, the similarity between his behavior and the energy dissi-
21 pation rate from the hydrodynamic turbulent flows is discussed. An intermittency
22 parameter $\mu \simeq 0.16$ from the lognormal model is found. To exclude the finite length
23 effect, a multifractal random walk is performed. The result indicates an intermittency
24 parameter $\mu \simeq 0.22$, which coincides well with the value of high Reynolds turbulent
25 flows. It suggests that Mr. Trump’s behavior is indeed intermittent, quantitatively
26 as well as qualitatively turbulent.

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27 I. INTRODUCTION

28 II. INTRODUCTION

29 Turbulence and turbulence-like phenomena are ubiquitous in nature. It has been found
30 in the evolution of the universe^{1,2}, the movement of the atmosphere or ocean^{3,4}, paintings
31 by Leonardo da Vinci^{5,6} and van Gogh⁷, collective motion of bacteria^{8,9}, the Bose-Einstein
32 condensate¹⁰, financial activity^{11,12} and the lithosphere deformation¹³, to name a few. In a
33 turbulent system, a large range of scales of motions or fluctuations are involved, leading to a
34 status between order and disorder, also known as chaos¹⁴. It is interesting to note that the
35 word “turbulence” or “turbulent” was originally used for a long time for the unpredictable
36 behavior of children or of a crowd and was adopted in fluid mechanics only at the end of
37 the XIXth century¹⁵. Today, it is still widely used to describe the stochastic fluctuations of
38 financial systems and social disorders^{16–18}. In this framework, any rigorous and long-term
39 data set measuring indicators belonging to social or psychological domains is interesting for
40 studying social or psychological intermittency or turbulence.

41 In this work, using data provided by the *Washington Post*, a multiscale analysis of false
42 or misleading claims of Mr. Trump is presented. It is found that the underlying dynamics
43 shows clear evidence of multifractality with an intermittency parameter equivalent to the
44 one of fully developed turbulence, which can be well characterized quantitatively in the
45 lognormal framework proposed by Kolmogorov in 1962¹⁹.

46 III. FALSE OR MISLEADING CLAIMS BY MR. TRUMP

47 The *Washington Post* provided a unique time series of the daily number of false or
48 misleading claims by Mr. Trump, the former president of the United States of America,
49 during his four-year presidential period from 20-01-2017 to 20-01-2021, see Figure 1 (a). A
50 fact check has been done by the journal to identify these false or misleading claims. There
51 are a total of 30,573 such claims in 1,354 days, with a mean value of roughly 23 per day and
52 a standard deviation of $\sigma \propto 37$. More details on the method and raw data can be found at
53 <https://www.washingtonpost.com>.

54 The visualization shows a very intermittent pattern, with the highest peak with a value of
55 503 on November 2, 2020, the day of the 2020 US presidential election. Similar intermittent

FIG. 1. (Color online) (a) Daily number of Mr. Trump’s false or misleading claims during his four-year presidential period from 20-01-2017 to 20-01-2021, showing an intermittent pattern. The right axis indicates the number of claims normalized by its daily mean value. (b) The energy dissipation rate ϵ measured in the atmospheric boundary layer, showing a similar intermittent pattern as in (a).

56 features are very often found for turbulent signals, such as, e.g., the energy dissipation rate
 57 ϵ collected in the atmospheric boundary layer; see Figure 1, (b). One significant feature of
 58 such intermittent time series is that it shows a huge time variation. For example, it can reach
 59 roughly 14 times its standard deviation and nearly 40 times its mean value for the energy
 60 dissipation rate ϵ , see Figure 1 (b). The empirical histogram (or probability density function
 61 - PDF) of this time series shows a roughly exponential-like tail in the range of $10 \sim 150$, see
 62 Figure 2 (a). This PDF may also be fitted, for values between 10 and 200, by a lognormal
 63 distribution, see the dashed line in Figure 2, (b). Due to the relatively low number of points
 64 considered (1,354 values is not high when considering PDFs), it is impossible here to decide
 65 if the empirical distribution is closer to exponential or to lognormal models.

FIG. 2. (Color online) (a) The empirical histogram in a semilogy plot with a bin width of 10. The dashed line is an exponential fit on the range $30 \sim 150$. (b) The lognormal distribution test. The dashed line is a lognormal distribution for reference.

FIG. 3. (Color online) Plot of the correlation function $\rho(\tau)$. For comparison, the correlation function of the shuffled time series is also shown as a thin line with a color band indicating the 95% confidence level. (b) The corresponding Fourier power spectrum, where the dashed line is a power-law fit on the range $0.002 \lesssim f \lesssim 0.2 \text{ day}^{-1}$, corresponding to a timescale $5 \lesssim \tau \lesssim 500$ days. The scatter dots are for the shuffled time series.

66 IV. LONG RANGE MEMORY AND INTERMITTENT PATTERN

67 In turbulence, but also for any stationary stochastic process, an integral timescale is
 68 defined as the integral of the autocorrelation function,

$$69 \quad \mathcal{T} = \int_0^{+\infty} \rho(\tau) d\tau \quad (1)$$

FIG. 4. (Color online) Experimental high-order $M_q(\tau)$ for $-1 \leq q \leq 4$. The dashed line is a power-law fit on the range $10 \lesssim \tau \lesssim 100$ days. (b) The measured scaling exponents $\mathcal{Z}(q)$ (Δ), where the box-plot is based on the estimation of the local scaling exponents $\mathcal{Z}(\tau, q)$ on the range $10 \lesssim \tau \lesssim 100$ days. For comparison, the measured $\mathcal{Z}(q)$ (\circ) for the shuffle experiment is also shown. The corresponding lognormal model fit is shown as dashed and dash-dotted lines.

70 where $\rho(\tau) = \langle N'(t)N'(t+\tau) \rangle_t / \sigma^2$ is the autocorrelation function, $N(t)$ is the number of
71 claims per day, τ the separation timescale, $N'(t) = N(t) - \langle N(t) \rangle_t$ the centered number of
72 claims, $\langle \cdot \rangle_t$ the time average, and σ the standard deviation. This is shown in Figure 3 (a):
73 it is found that the measured $\rho(\tau)$ slowly decays to zero. The integral timescale \mathcal{T} is found
74 to be 25 ± 1 days. The Fourier power spectrum can be estimated as the Fourier transform
75 of the correlation function. It displays a power-law decay of the form,

$$76 \quad E(f) \propto f^{-\beta} \quad (2)$$

77 with an experimental scaling exponent $\beta \simeq 0.84$. This power-law decay is expected for the
78 intermittency in turbulence. It has been found since the 1960s²⁰ and indicates that the large
79 values in the dissipation field are correlated^{5,14}. Here, similarly, such a result indicates a
80 structure in the successive false claims. To test this, a shuffle experiment was performed, by
81 considering the same data but destroying the time information by taking randomly chosen
82 values among the original data. This way the PDF of the data is not modified, but the time
83 information is lost. The results are also compared to the correlation plot and the Fourier
84 power spectrum (Figure 3). It shows that the long-range memory effect is destroyed by
85 randomly shifting the phase: The power spectrum is, as expected, constant, indicative of a

86 white noise. All these observations show that the number of claims $N(t)$ of Mr. Trump have
 87 stochastic variations, with some structure in them, as shown by the autocorrelation function
 88 and the power spectrum. They share some degree of similarity with the energy dissipation
 89 rate ϵ for high Reynolds number hydrodynamic turbulent flows.

90 V. A MULTIFRACTAL STUDY

91 A. Multifractal with log-normal model

92 To further characterize the intermittent features of the number of false claims, a multiscale
 93 coarse-graining approach is applied. This was originally proposed by A.N. Kolmogorov for
 94 the dissipation field in turbulence¹⁹. The scale-dependent coarse-grained number of claims
 95 is written as^{14,21},

$$96 \quad N_\tau(t) = \frac{1}{\tau} \int_{t' \leq \tau} N(t + t') dt' \quad (3)$$

97 where τ is the timescale. The statistical moments of the coarse-grained quantity $N_\tau(t)$ are
 98 then studied. They are expected to follow a power-law behavior of the form,

$$99 \quad M_q(\tau) = \langle N_\tau(t)^q \rangle_t \propto \left(\frac{T_0}{\tau} \right)^{\mathcal{Z}(q)}, \quad (4)$$

100 where T_0 is a timescale, $q \geq -1$ due to statistical convergence and $\mathcal{Z}(q)$ is the moment
 101 scaling function. If this relation is satisfied, the log-log plots of the moments versus τ should
 102 be straight lines, their slopes giving estimates of the moment function. This is shown in
 103 Figure 4(a). This figure confirms the power-law relation in the range $10 \lesssim \tau \lesssim 100$ days.
 104 Here, $\mu = \mathcal{Z}(2)$ is the intermittency parameter^{5,14}. We find a value of $\mu = 0.16 \pm 0.01$, which
 105 is surprisingly close to the value found for energy dissipation in fully developed turbulence
 106 $\mu = 0.25 \pm 0.05$ ^{5,14,22}.

107 The simplest and more widely accepted analytical model for $\mathcal{Z}(q)$ is a lognormal model
 108 of the form,

$$109 \quad \mathcal{Z}(q) = \frac{\mu}{2}(q^2 - q) \quad (5)$$

110 The measured values of the moment scaling function, together with the lognormal fit with
 111 $\mu = 0.16$ are shown in Figure 4(b). It is found that the lognormal fit is very good for
 112 moments from 0 to 4.

FIG. 5. (Color online) Recompiled experimental scaling exponents $\mathcal{Z}(q)$ provided by Eq. 5 and 9, where the curves for the multifractal random walk are shown as \bullet without shuffle and \blacksquare with shuffle.

113 B. A multifractal random walk test

114 To exclude the artifact of the finite-length effect and verify this intermittent feature, a
 115 multifractal random walk (MRW) test is performed. A MRW time series is generated as

$$x(t) = \int_0^t N(t')^h dB_h(t'), \quad (6)$$

116 where $B_h(t)$ is the fractional Brownian motion; h is the Hurst number that characterizing
 117 the scaling behavior of $x(t)$; and $N(t)$ provides an intermittency correction. The high-order
 118 moment of the structure function of $x(t)$ is expected to obey a power-law behavior,

$$S_q(\tau) = \langle |x(t + \tau) - x(t)|^q \rangle_t \propto \tau^{\zeta_h(q)} \quad (7)$$

119 Due to the lognormality of $N(t)$, see Fig.2 (b), the measured scaling exponents $\zeta_h(q)$ should
 120 obey the following scaling relation¹⁹,

$$\zeta_h(q) = qh - \mathcal{Z}_h(qh) \quad (8)$$

121 where $\mathcal{Z}(q)$ is provided by Eq. 5. The scaling exponent $\mathcal{Z}_h(q)$ is thus rewritten as

$$\mathcal{Z}_h(q) = q - \zeta_h(q/h) \quad (9)$$

122 $\mathcal{Z}_h(q)$ is expected to be h -independent since the intermittency correction is provided only
123 by $N(t)$. The numerical experiment with $0.5 \lesssim h < 1$ confirms the validation of the above
124 scaling relation, i.e., Eq. 9 with a measured intermittency parameter $\mu \simeq 0.22$, see Figure 5.

125 VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

126 In this work, we have considered a time series of four years of daily false claims from M.
127 Trump, as provided by the *Washington post*. This time series was found to be intermittent
128 and was studied with methods borrowed from the field of turbulence, more precisely for the
129 dissipation field in fully developed turbulence. It was found that Mr. Trump's false or mis-
130 leading claims, seen as a time series, behave like the energy dissipation rate ϵ in turbulence.
131 Both variables show a significant intermittent pattern, which can be further characterized
132 in the lognormal multiplicative cascade framework proposed by the mathematician A. N.
133 Kolmogorov in the 1960s for high Reynolds number hydrodynamic turbulent flows^{5,19}. The
134 lognormal model with the intermittency parameter $\mu = 0.16$ was found to fit the data well
135 for time scales from 10 to 100 days. To exclude the effect of finite data length, a multifractal
136 random walk test is performed, showing an intermittency parameter $\mu = 0.22$, which is in
137 good agreement with the value of hydrodynamic turbulence.

138 Such intermittency with long-range correlations shows that there is a structure in the time
139 succession of false claims. They are clearly correlated, showing stochastic behavior, which
140 is not noise. Considering human behavior, this can be interpreted by a memory effect: calm
141 periods with a low number of false claims tend to be aggregated, and symmetrically, agitated
142 days with a large number of wrong claims are indicative of an anger mood, which lasts for
143 several days: large values of daily false claims come together. This dynamical structure,
144 with a correlation time of 25 days, is another important finding of this work.

145 As aforementioned, the word "turbulence" or "turbulent" has been used for a long time
146 to describe the unpredictable behavior of children or of a crowd. With the help of the
147 multiscale analysis, it is shown here for the first time that human behavior might share the
148 same intermittent pattern as the one of hydrodynamic turbulent flows. In other words, Mr.
149 Trump's behavior is turbulent in a qualitative and quantitative understanding of the word.

150 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

151 The raw data is free accessed at <https://www.washingtonpost.com>. A copy of the time
152 series and the Python version of the analysis code can be found at <https://github.com>.

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